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ANNOTATION A comparative study of the units of politeness in different linguistic cultures becomes relevant due to a number of objective reasons: international and interethnic contacts in various spheres of human activity have expanded, interest in the national identity of different peoples has increased, which has increased the importance of research in the field of intercultural communication. In this regard, it is of interest to study polite linguistic units in the speech of representatives of Uzbek and English communicative cultures: through the prism of politeness, one can trace the national and cultural characteristics of Uzbek and Englishmen, present the main components of the communicative behavior of different people, discover some causes of communicative failures, emotional discomfort.

Key words: politeness, linguistics, culture, pragmatics, expressions, strategy.

Various dictionaries describe the notion of politeness in many different ways. For instance, Merriam-Webster dictionary gives several definitions for the term politeness, one of which is: *"marked by an appearance of consideration, tact, deference, or courtesy."* Although politeness is not a direct synonym for diplomacy and tact, they are certainly related. For this reason, studying communicating, it is essential to pay attention to diplomacy, tact and analyze the idea of politeness covering various academic approaches to this concept. Politeness assumes that as a human being we all have face and we are all in need of something. Considering sociological variables of a face-threatening act, researchers analyze three variables of *weight*: power, distance, and rank. **Power** refers to the dynamic power produced by speaker and received by hearer. In this kind of conversation speaker takes into

account hearer's level if he or she is superior, subordinate, or at the same social level. Next one is *distance*, **which** refers to the amount of social distance between speaker and listener if they are close friends or distant colleagues. Finally, *rank* refers to the cultural ranking of the subject -- the degree of sensitivity of the topic within a particular culture. For instance, a woman's age and weight are considered to be very sensitive topics within European culture, while some other countries' women like to share answers of these two personal questions, not considering them as sensitive topics. Politeness theory posits and politeness strategy depends upon the social circumstances in which the speech act occurs. Namely, to whom are you speaking, what is your social relationship with that person, and what is the topic? There are a number of scholars who made a contribution in discovery of politeness strategies and its socio-pragmatic role in speech act. One of the adopted linguists Levinson considers pragmatics as the study of language and context, which are important to understand language. Studying language cannot be separated from situation, from speech uttered in particular situation. For this reason, pragmatics includes the relevant context or situation, instead of the language usage itself. According to Yule, pragmatics studies contextual meaning as he claims the study of meaning is communicated by a speaker (a writer) and interpreted by a listener (a reader). In this way, pragmatics involves interpretation what people intend to say in particular context and how context impacts on readers. Taking into account above given information, we can conclude that pragmatics is the study of meaning based on the context, which means when we want to understand the meaning of the words we must see the context when the speakers utter the words.

❖ *Face: positive and negative face*

According to linguists Brown and Levinson our notion of face is derived from the English folk term, which ties face up with notions of being embarrassed or humiliated or "losing face". So, while communicating face is something that is emotionally invested, maintained, lost or enhanced in conversation and should be

constantly attended in interaction as people try to cooperate and receive each other's cooperation while communicating and interacting. If people maintain each other's conversation and feel being maintained, they feel free and confident as face mostly depends on maintenance and people can be expected to defend their faces if threatened, and in defending their own to threaten others face.

Face is visual representation of personality and *Positive face* is the positive self-image or 'personality' that is appreciated and approved by interactants". If this kind of face seems to be liked and approved by others, same members of a group can easily recognize it and people can share their opinions effortlessly. Positive face is related to one of politeness strategies known as positive politeness. On the other hand, *Negative face* highlights more freedom and people feel more confidence not to be imposed by others. This kind of face has everyone, which can be seen in daily conversation. This kind of face is related to negative politeness and hearer can show different acts that show negative politeness. Two linguists Levinson and Brown, who worked on politeness, claim that negative politeness involves freedom of action and freedom from imposition.

❖ *Face threatening act*

Brown and Levinson consider a face-threatening act as damaging the face of hearer by acting opposite to listener's desire. Speaker may use face-threatening act for many different reasons, the most crucial one is to influence on listener and minimize desperation making listener offended. Thus, politeness strategies are mainly developed on purpose to save the speaker's face or the hearer's face. Briefly, politeness strategies are used to lessen face-threatening act and support relationship. However, the way we convey our opinions may vary relying on ranking, power, age, position, which means the way people choose a certain politeness strategies and certain speech act to influence others.

According to Brown and Levinson, politeness measures social distance between the speaker and the listener, which means politeness, is the power that controls imposition in one culture that helps to feel comfortable with someone who

has higher position. The phenomena above indicate that the degree of relationship has important part influence them to use the certain politeness strategies. It also implies that it is necessary for the speaker and the hearer to be aware of the usage certain politeness strategies in appropriate condition and situation to maintain the relationship in social interaction. Relying on Brown and Levinson's theory face-threatening acts can be *verbal*, **when the speaker verbalizes** words or language, *paraverbal* is conveyed in the characteristics of speech with the help of tone or inflexion, or *non-verbal* using facial expressions or body language. As two scholars claim face-threatening acts may threaten not only the speaker's face, but also the listener's face as well. Positive face-threatening acts damages listener's positive face and self-image in the example of expressions of disapproval, accusations, criticism, and disagreements, which shows that the speaker does not care about the listener's positive face using *taboo* words or emotional topics, interruptions, and expressions of violent emotions. Positive face and self-image of the listener can be threatened by the speaker including apologies, namely accepting of being wrong, confessions, and a loss of emotional control. For instance:

"I don't like that outfit at all."

"You ate all my cheese, didn't you?!"

"I'm definitely better at maths than you."

"Didn't your last partner cheat on you all the time?"

"I'm all over the place right now and haven't done any housework in weeks!"

Speech acts that threaten the listener's negative face and limits their personal freedoms include making the listener to do something in the future, such as giving an order, making a request, giving a reminder, or making a threat. Thus, face-threatening acts can make the speaker to express a strong emotion towards the listener that typically requires some form of positive reaction. For example, paying a compliment and expecting a compliment in return. Let's have a look at some examples that threaten the listener's negative face:

"*I really like you.*" – Sometimes it is considered polite, however in this situation the speaker does not really like the person, but expects the listener to say something civil in return.

"*Pick that up for me.*"

"*If you don't apologize, I won't speak to you again.*"

❖ *Politeness Strategies*

Politeness, according to Yule is interpersonal relations that maintains human interaction lessening potential conflict inherent human communication. Thus, politeness is defined as a means that helps to be aware of another person's face. Face means public self-image of person. *Politeness strategies* are essential to give messages to save the listener's face when face-threatening act are predictable. Two scholar Brown and Levinson, who worked on politeness in communication, consider politeness strategies save hearer's face and maintain the relationship in social interaction. They argue that every member of a society has a face, which is called self-image, and they analyze four main types of politeness strategies: positive politeness, negative politeness, bald on record and off record.

Positive politeness strategies aim to lessen the threat to the listener's positive face. They are mainly used to make hearer feel comfortable and feel good about themselves, their interests or possessions. Positive politeness strategies are used in situations, where everyone knows each other quite well. Politeness in conversation means respecting the feelings of others, which helps to improve your relationships with others, help to build respect and rapport, boost your self-esteem and confidence, and improve your communication skills. In sociolinguistics and conversation analysis, politeness strategies are speech acts that express opinions and feelings of others and lessen threat to self-image in particular social context. Politeness is very important in life and can be seen as a great virtue. However, a polite person will always please others with this polite behavior, respectful words and good manners. Polite people consider for the feelings of others as politeness is

one of the central features of human communication, which is expressed differently in all cultures.

Positive politeness creates positive atmosphere with the help of compliments, encouragement, joking, even the use of "white lies." Usually, positive politeness strategies aim to avoid giving offense by emphasizing friendliness, including criticism with compliments, using common jokes, nicknames honorifics, tag questions, special discourse markers (please), and in-group jargon and slang. Sometimes this is called sandwich feedback as there is always a positive comment before and after a criticism. In communication positive politeness strategies emphasize friendliness and camaraderie between the speaker and listener, which means the speaker's and hearer's wants are similar in some occasions and they can maintain each other, where first of all speaker takes into account hearer's wants, interests, needs, or goods, secondly the speaker can highlight listener's interest, approval or sympathy and emotions. Finally, the speaker can demonstrate eagerness to the hearer. Moreover, the speaker can also use in-group markers, including in-group language or dialect, use of jargon or slang, and linguistic contractions, which shows that both the speaker and listener belong to the same social group, such as a work culture or religious affiliation. For example, "Dude, you know..." or, "Brother, I'd like to speak with you..." (Accidental love). The speaker may also find agreement with the hearer discussing safe and familiar topics using repetitions. What is more interesting, the speaker can also avoid disagreement with the hearer by employing a token agreement, a pseudo-agreement, a white lie, or hedging an opinion. The speaker can also predict of the hearer's wants and attitudes, presuppose the hearer's values are the same as the speaker's values, presuppose familiarity in the speaker-hearer relationship, and presuppose the hearer's knowledge on the topic. One more effective way to invoke familiarity between speaker and hearer is to use humor or joking, which claims their cooperation. These include asserting or presupposing the speaker's knowledge of, and concern for, the hearer's wants, offering or promising, being optimistic,

including both speaker and hearer in a target activity, giving or asking for reasons, and assuming or asserting reciprocity. Finally, to establish positive politeness effectively and to achieve listener's fulfillment, the speaker can find some ways like giving a gift, which helps to capture sympathy, understanding and corporation. Good examples for positive politeness are compliments: *"I really like the way you've done this,"* or, *"It took me forever to figure this out, but what I eventually came to was..."* or, *"You know it's always important to me to do the best job I can, and I know the same is true for you. That's why I think we should pay attention to this piece a little,"* or, *"I really like the way you approach this here. I think this other part might be a little stronger with a similar approach."* In this examples, the speaker is bringing his or her own opinions into the agreement by polite phrases, highlighting similar and familiar words that makes hearer comfortable and puts the content under discussion.

On the other hand, *negative politeness strategies* pay attention to negative faces, keeping a distance between the speaker and the speech partner and does not interfere with each other's territory. Speakers use negative politeness strategies to give a choice for partners and avoid compulsion, highlighting the interests of others by using apologies, or by asking questions that give the possibility to answer "no". For instance, at university you may ask your friend: *"Sorry to bother, can I borrow three hundred dollars if you don't need it now?"* Another example: *"Sorry, should have called you, but Will didn't mean to bother, but maybe you could tell me when we should go to hospital?"* (Me before you, jojo Moyes, 2012, p299). If the listener has choices, this will effect on politeness. The more likely the answer to "no" is given, the more polite the speech is. While positive politeness seeks the hearer's positive and approachable self-image through recognizing the hearer's needs in communication taking into account listener's wishes, desires and appreciating hearer's opinions socially, *negative politeness* enhances the hearer's need for freedom of action and freedom from imposition in making his or her own decisions. First, in communication negative

politeness requires being conventionally indirect. Negative politeness strategies refer to the listener's negative face and avoids hearer's imposition and the feelings of awkwardness or embarrassment. Such sentences include hedging (words or phrases that describe probability and soften statements by giving less-than-certain phrases such as *perhaps, might, can, or could*) lessening the imposition, apologizing, being indirect, and using questions rather than commands. For instance, *"I don't suppose you know where the library is, do you?"* » - (being indirect and hedging) or *"Could you print this off for me? It is only a few pages and will not take long!"* »- (minimizing the imposition), *"I'm so sorry, but could you help me?"* – (being apologetic). Moreover, being pessimistic is also one of the strategies, which will not impose the hearer: *"I'm sure you won't want to do this..."* – (minimizing the imposition) *«It is a small thing I need..."*, *"you know much more about this than I do..."* – (giving deference). The speaker also can express his or her desire not to impinge the hearer through apologizing strategies that include admitting the impingement: *"I know this is a big deal..."*- (indicating reluctance), *"I hate to ask this..."* – (begging forgiveness for giving overwhelming task). One more strategy that helps not to impinge the hearer is impersonalizing the speaker and hearer. These strategies include using passive and circumstantial voices: *"It's generally done this way..."*, replacing "I" and "you" with indefinites: *"people tend to..."*, pluralizing "I" and "you": *"We don't always know what we're up against..."*, and avoiding use of "I" and "you" all together. For this reason, negative politeness comments might include, *"some people might approach the situation in this way,"* or *"I think I might do it differently, but of course whatever you think is best,"* or *"I don't know a lot about this but it seems that this approach might be reasonable and the situation"* or *"I know you know a lot more about this than I do, but it seems to me..."* In these examples, the speaker is recognizing and addressing the hearer's right to make his or her own decisions freely, thus attending to the hearer's negative face needs.

Next politeness strategy in speech act that is called *bald on-record* aims not to limit listener's freedom or to threat listener's face, but to avoid some impeding urgent situation. If the speaker knows the hearer well and there is no risk to threat listener's face, this kind of speech can be used highlighting essential point without polite additional words that soften language. For example:

"*Watch out!*" - Time of urgency.

"*Your headlights are on!*" - In the interest of the listener.

"*Eat up!*" - if the speaker and listener know each other well, this would be deemed acceptable. This politeness strategy comparatively short and precise, which makes it clear avoiding ambiguity. The positives of this strategy include: being honest and straight, avoiding confusion by not using unnecessary words or phrases, and not putting pressure on the listener in the time of urgency.

The last politeness strategy of Brown and Levinson is the *off-record or indirect strategy*. In this strategy the speaker uses some serious indirectness, that's to say, the speaker avoids saying face-threatening act directly. Instead, the speakers' keeps ambiguity, and it is up to the listener to interpret them. It is helpful not only for the speaker, but also for the listener as well since the speaker does not impose the listener and listener may show himself as a generous and helpful person. However, this strategy relies heavily on [pragmatics](#) to convey the intended meaning. For example:

Speaker: "*Is there a free chair over there?*"

Listener: "*Yes, here you go.*" (They give the speaker a chair).

Speaker: "*I have a headache.*"

Listener "*Oh dear. Here, take some of my painkillers.*"

Both dialogues show that the speaker never actually asks for anything and therefore the imposition on the listener is reduced. Advantages of this strategy include getting credit for being tactful and respectful, avoiding responsibility of face-threatening act. This strategy is very indirect and relies on implication. Although the speaker is indirect and ambiguous, he or she intends the listener

encode the meaning behind his speech. There are several ways to accomplish off-record politeness, one of which is to give hints or clues of association presuppose, understate, overstate, use tautologies, use contradictions, be ironic, use metaphors, and use rhetorical questions. Another way of conveying this strategy is to be intentionally vague or ambiguous, also over-generalizing, displacing the hearer, and being incomplete by using ellipsis. We can see some examples that include above mentioned strategy:

A) *"What do you think about these pants?"*

B) *"I think you have a lot a very nice clothes in your closet, especially pants."*

A) *"Do you think we should leave at 7 or 7:30?"*

B) *"I think your sister is a stickler for punctuality."*

A) *"I think I'd like to watch the football game."*

B) *"Yes, a little violent aggression is a good way to spend a Monday night."*

In this dialogue, speaker B is giving suggestions to speaker A, but the reader may not understand due to ambiguity and indirectness. However, speaker A will understand the implications offered by speaker B thanks to given context and their relationship. One downside of this strategy is that, hearer will not clarify and misunderstand the speaker as the implications are so vague. This is the nature of off-record politeness. Many researchers have contributed to improvement politeness theory and many may believe that everyone has a sense for what politeness. But, it's really hard to describe when someone asks you to define it. One thing that all scholars agree upon is that politeness is something that is learned or acquired. We are not born into it, but rather socialized into it. Further, because we are socialized into it, it naturally follows that different cultures have different ideas of what it is, and how it should be appropriately employed.

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